

SOCIAL AND CULTURAL ASPECTS OF THE EMPIRICAL PROBLEMS IN THE TRANSITION TO A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Pavliashvili S.

Georgian Academy of Sciences,

Member, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, Tbilisi, Georgia

Tokmazishvili M.

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor, ALTE University,

Tbilisi, Georgia

Abstract

The research addresses the social and cultural challenges of the circular economy, focusing on its transformation, consumer behavior, and cultural diversity. It systematizes and prioritizes social problems, which is crucial for defining the focal points of relevant state policies and planning the multidimensional parameters necessary for the transition to a circular economy. The study also characterizes the directions, barriers, and priorities for advancing a circular economy, both theoretically and through practical assessments.

Keywords: circular economy, consumer behavior, cultural diversity, circular models, circular practices and policy.

Introduction

The transition to a circular economy and the development of a sustainable economy are accompanied by social and cultural changes, as well as shifts in consumer behavior and lifestyle. However, this transition does not occur without challenges and takes on different forms in various countries.

This article focuses on social and cultural barriers. Based on a review of the literature, it characterizes the obstacles encountered in different sectors of the economy. Through their identification and systematization, priorities have been established, which are crucial for defining the focal points of relevant state policy and planning multidimensional parameters. Given the limited availability of statistical data on the circular economy, the research relies on empirical methods, the generalization of scientific literature, observable evidence, and comparative analysis.

1. Social Barriers

The circular economy, as an economic model, differs from the traditional linear model by emphasizing the repeated use of resources and products, reducing waste, and increasing the positive impact on the environment. It involves companies, consumers, and governments throughout the entire product lifecycle to ensure ecological sustainability, helping to conserve natural resources and mitigate climate change in the future.

As noted in much of the scientific literature, one of the most significant barriers to transitioning to a circular economy is the lack of awareness and persistence of traditional production and consumption practices (Juana Camacho-Otero, etc., 2018). The public has not yet fully comprehended the long-term impact of the circular economy concept and its potential benefits. Resistance to change, along with conventional thinking and habits, hinders the shift towards a sustainable and circular economy. Therefore, increasing public awareness and education is crucial for its successful implementation (Pavliashvili, etc., 2024). Without widespread understanding and support, driving change at the consumer level may be challenging.

Low awareness of the circular economy is manifested in various ways. The literature frequently highlights issues such as insufficient stakeholder education,

a lack of understanding of circular principles, and other related deficiencies (Akinwale, 2023; Jéssica dos Santos Leite Gonella, etc., 2023).

Sectoral Aspects

Research is also being conducted on sectoral aspects. For example, in the construction industry, there is often limited awareness of the potential for reusing and recycling building materials. Buildings are frequently demolished without recovering materials such as steel, concrete, or wood waste, which could be used in new construction projects. Demolition often results in debris that contributes to waste and resource depletion (Abdulaziz AlJaber, etc., 2024).

In agriculture, farmers and agribusiness may not be fully recognize the benefits of circular practices, such as processing food waste, where organic waste is turned into fertilizer. Instead, they often rely on synthetic fertilizers, which contribute to environmental degradation and resource depletion (Juan F. Velasco-Muñoz, etc., 2021). Similarly, many consumers and businesses in the food industry do not effectively manage food waste through circular methods.

In Georgia, the adoption of circular principles faces criticism in retail, agriculture, and the construction industry. Both consumers and entrepreneurs often underestimate the importance of sustainable packaging, the reuse of single-use plastics, and the availability of alternatives such as biodegradable materials or reusable containers (Pavliashvili, etc., 2022; Tokmazishvili, etc., 2024). This is partly due to a lack of awareness about the environmental benefits of circular packaging decisions.

2. Cultural Barriers

Cultural barriers to the circular economy stem from society's attitudes, values, and behaviors. These barriers include social norms, cultural preferences, and resistance to change (Kirchherr, etc., 2018). Among them, a strong attachment to new products and cultural resistance to change—rooted in established social behaviors—are particularly significant. The following aspects are noteworthy:

Traditional Perception of Social Status

One barrier to implementing the circular model is the traditional view of social status. In Georgia, as in

other countries, car ownership is regarded as a symbol of social standing and personal success. This cultural preference for ownership creates resistance to practices such as car-sharing, leasing, or other business models aligned with circular economy principles.

Stigma Around Second-Hand Goods

There is a cultural stigma surrounding second-hand products and a cultural norm that favors gifting new items. New products and innovation are associated with wealth and social status, while the consumption of second-hand or recycled products is perceived as a sign of poverty. In some consumer cultures, broken or outdated devices are replaced rather than repaired, based on the belief that new items are inherently superior. This trend is particularly true in countries with a high standard of living. As economy grows, so does the accumulation of unused waste, further limiting the development of circular practices.

Single-Use Consumption Culture

From an environmental perspective, the culture of single-use consumption often conflicts with the principles of a circular economy. For example, in the food and beverage industry, the widespread use of single-use plastics, disposable cups, and cutlery, is frequently driven by their practicality. This reliance on single-use items creates a significant barrier to adopting reusable alternatives and reducing waste, as they have become cultural norms.

Traditional Business Practices

Deeply entrenched traditional business practices also hinder the adoption of new models. Many companies remain firmly committed to traditional linear business models that prioritize production and sales over sustainability, particularly in transitional economies like Georgia. In contrast, developed countries such as Germany and Japan are increasingly shifting toward sustainable circular economy models—especially in industries like automotive manufacturing, where transitioning requires significant changes in design, production, and business strategy. Consequently, while highly developed countries have greater opportunities for new product development, in Georgia, circular economy principles are more commonly applied in areas such as car and motorcycle repair.

Entrenched Consumerism and Materialism

Widespread consumerism and materialism, particularly in the luxury goods market, pose another barrier to the circular economy. Owning the latest and most expensive products—such as designer handbags, watches, or cars—is associated with success and social status. This cultural focus on ownership and wealth undermines the promotion of more sustainable consumption patterns.

Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior is a significant barrier to implementing circular economy practices (Fátima Vidal-Ayuso, et al., 2023). One major obstacle is consumers' preference for new products. For instance, they prefer to purchase a new item (such as clothing) rather than opting for second-hand or refurbished items, even when the latter may be of high quality. Despite growing environmental awareness, the demand for new products remains strong, undermining circular initiatives like

clothing rental or resale platforms. Circular consumption typically occurs only for high-value and single-use products, such as wedding dresses, national costumes, theater costumes, etc.

Disposal habits and a lack of a recycling culture also hinder the adoption of the circular model. In the realm of consumer electronics, many consumers do not attempt to repair old devices, viewing them as having depreciated value. Old smartphones, laptops, and other electronic devices often end up in general waste, despite containing valuable materials that could be recovered. The continued preference for new devices exacerbates this problem, limiting the reuse of precious resources in new products.

In the consumer goods sector, excessive consumption and impulse-buying culture present further challenges to the adoption of circular economy practices. Consumers frequently purchase cheap, low-quality household items, reinforcing a "buy-use-dispose" mentality. This demand for inexpensive, single-use products makes it difficult for companies to develop durable, repairable, or reusable alternatives.

Many consumers are unaware of the circular options available to them, such as repair services, product service models, or zero-waste stores. For example, in the electronics industry, consumers may replace washing machines or refrigerators instead of repairing them due to ingrained consumption patterns. As wealth increases, so does the preference for new products.

High demands regarding quality and hygiene hinder the culture of circular consumption. In the personal care and cosmetics industry, consumers are reluctant to purchase products made from recycled materials or to use reusable containers due to traditional notions of quality and hygiene. In their view, these products are considered less sanitary or of lower quality, which impedes the adoption of circular models.

Circular practices often require changes in consumer behavior, which may be perceived as inconvenient. In the food sector, bringing reusable containers for purchasing is seen as more effortful than buying pre-packaged goods, limiting the adoption of sustainable retail practices.

Consumers often focus on short-term costs and choose cheaper, lower-quality goods and materials (for example, in construction and home renovation) that may not be durable or recyclable, rather than opting for higher-quality, sustainable alternatives. The widespread use of cheap vinyl or laminated flooring instead of more durable and recyclable materials such as bamboo or wood serves as a barrier to the adoption of more sustainable, circular construction materials.

Consumer culture regarding ownership sharing and leasing is at odds with the principles of the circular economy. In the automotive industry, many consumers prefer car ownership over car-sharing or leasing.

There is also a low level of trust in secondary markets. In the electronics and technology sectors, consumers are typically skeptical about the quality and reliability of second-hand or refurbished products. This lack of trust hinders their willingness to choose circular options, even when these options provide economic and environmental benefits.

Finally, consumers resist change. In many industries, consumers are accustomed to traditional linear consumption patterns and are reluctant to change their behaviors. For example, in the food and beverage industry, consumers are hesitant to switch from single-use plastic bottles to reusable ones. This resistance to change can be a significant barrier to the implementation of more sustainable practices.

Conclusion

People's consumption-related social behaviors and cultural attitudes are based on the belief that waste is not a resource but rather a problem to be solved by the government. Consumers adhere to traditional practices. These attitudes and cultural factors have a profound impact on consumer behavior, business practices, and societal outlook, which in turn hinders the implementation of circular economy principles and the development of circular initiatives. Overcoming these barriers often requires not only technological and regulatory changes, but also influencing cultural norms and values. Changing consumer behavior and overcoming these barriers is achievable through a long-term effort to raise awareness, shift perceptions, and incentivize consumers to adopt more sustainable, circular practices. This effort relies on two key measures – education and encouragement to participate in the circular economy (Circular Transformation of Industries, 2024).

A just transition framework for the circular economy has the potential to identify opportunities that reduce waste and stimulate product innovation, while at the same time making a positive contribution to sustainable development. A just transition is necessary to reduce inequalities both within and between countries and to meet the commitments of sustainable development goals, ensuring that no one is left behind.

References

1. Juana Camacho-Otero, Casper Boks, Ida Nilstad Pettersen, Consumption in the Circular Economy: A Literature Review, *Sustainability*, 2018, 10(8), 2758; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10082758>
2. Akinwale, Y. O. (2023). Awareness and adoption of circular economy in the consumption and production value-chain among MSMEs towards sustainable development. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 16 (4), 537–546. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2023.2247924>
3. Jéssica dos Santos Leite Gonella, Moacir Godinho Filho, Gilberto Miller Devós Ganga, Hengky Latan, Charbel Jose Chiappetta Jabbour, Towards a regenerative economy: An innovative scale to measure people's awareness of the circular economy, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 421, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138390>; <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652623025489>
4. Abdulaziz AlJaber, Pedro Martinez-Vazquez, Charalampos Baniotopoulos, Attitudes, Barriers, and

Enablers through a Case Study in Saudi Arabia, *Sustainability*, 2024, 16 (3), 1296; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16031296>

5. Juan F. Velasco-Muñoz, Joan Manuel F. Mendoza, José A. Aznar-Sánchez, Alejandro Gallego-Schmid, Circular economy implementation in the agricultural sector: Definition, strategies and indicators, Resources, *Conservation and Recycling*, Volume 170, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021>; <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921344921002275>

6. Julian Kirchherr, Laura Piscicelli, Ruben Bour, Erica Kostense-Smit, Jennifer Muller, Anne Hui-brehtse-Truijens, Marko Hekkert, Barriers to the Circular Economy: Evidence From the European Union (EU), *Ecological Economics*, Volume 150, 2018, p. 264-272,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2018.04.028>.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921800917317573>

7. Fátima Vidal-Ayuso, Anna Akhmedova, Carmen Jaca, The circular economy and consumer behaviour: Literature review and research directions, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 418, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137824>.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652623019820>

8. Circular Transformation of Industries: The Role of Partnerships, World Economic Forum, White Paper, January, 2024, [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpajpcglefindmkaj/https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Circular_Transformation_of_Industries_2024.pdf](https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Circular_Transformation_of_Industries_2024.pdf)

9. M. Tokmazishvili, S. Pavliashvili, CHALLENGES OF FARMERS' EDUCATION SYSTEM IN GEORGIA, Foundations and trends in Modern Learning, Berlin Germany 7-8.03 2024, Proceedings of the 5th International Scientific Conference, <https://ojs.publisher.agency/index.php/FTML/issue/view/73/186>, <https://ojs.publisher.agency/index.php/FTML/issue/view/73/186>, 2024, p. 179-183

10. M. Tokmazishvili, S. Pavliashvili, The methodological approaches to the Integration of the Circular and Sustainable Economies The scientific heritage (Budapest, Hungary), No 94 (94) (2022), pp.18-22. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpajpcglefindmkaj/https://www.scientific-heritage.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/The-scientific-heritage-No-94-94-2022.pdf](https://www.scientific-heritage.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/The-scientific-heritage-No-94-94-2022.pdf)

11. S. Pavliashvili, M. Tokmazishvili, Global economic and legal problems of introducing the circular economy and Georgia, Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science, 2024, #145, pp. 51-55./., <https://nor-ijournal.com/2024/11/26/njd-145/>.

12. M. Tokmazishvili, Solomon Pavliashvili, Green Loans and the Vulnerability of Industries: The Case of Georgia, Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science, №114/2023, p. 16-23. ISSN 3453-9875, https://nor-ijournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/NJD_114.pdf, p 16-23.